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Spatial Ability in Engineering Education: Working Towards an Integrated Learning Approach

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INTRODUCTION

Engineering is a collaborative and complex activity which demands the use of a broad range of skills and perspectives [1]. The desired attributes of an engineer have long been the focus for engineering educators and will continue to be discussed throughout the progression of the profession as a result of its dynamic and evolutionary nature. Despite the progression of the profession, biologically primary and secondary abilities will always be necessary for engineers to perform in their key roles such as problem solving. Biologically primary abilities are those which an individual is born with (innate) and do not require direct development [2], or cannot be directly developed such as information processing [3]. Biologically secondary abilities, such as domain-specific communication skills [3], can be acquired through education and training [2] and are therefore the core focus of education programmes.

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As the desired attributes of an engineer continuously evolve, engineering education focuses on developing knowledge, skills, and abilities through educational programmes to support students in consolidating these three elements. While biologically primary skills such as information processing and communication skills are central to information being understood [2][3], biologically secondary abilities, such as technical knowledge and transversal skills, may be fundamental to achieving an integrated learning experience whereby knowledge, skills, and abilities may be truly consolidated.

Technical knowledge and skills encompass a broad range of abilities such as science and engineering fundamentals, applications, and practice [6][7]. Similarly, there are a broad range of transversal skills used in the context of engineering education, such as discipline-specific communication, creativity, and problem-solving [1][6][7]. Spatial ability, a transversal skill, is the focus of this paper.

Spatial ability has been attributed to the successful acquisition and development of both technical and transversal engineering skills [4][5][7][8][9][10][11][12]. Therefore, spatial ability is a fundamental element to consider when aiming to achieve an integrated teaching and learning experience in engineering education. Although spatial ability is an innate ability, spatial skills are biologically secondary abilities and therefore may be developed to support and compliment the innate spatial ability of an individual. Throughout this paper the role of spatial ability and spatial skills to support an integrated learning experience being achieved through engineering education is examined.

1 ENGINEERING SKILLS

The concept of technical knowledge and skill is utilised to classify abilities such as science and engineering fundamentals, applications, and practice [6][7][16][17]. Through the literature, transversal skills are referred to as 'soft', 'non-technical' or 'life' skills [4][6][7][16][17], among a range of other terms. Throughout this paper they will be referred to as transversal skills. In the context of engineering education, transversal skills include discipline-specific communication, creativity, critical-thinking, discipline-specific problem-solving, and spatial ability/skills [6][7][16][17].

The requirement for technical knowledge and skill in engineering is irrefutable [1][5][6][7][16][17]. These abilities are important for engineers to successfully perform in their key technical roles. However, in a rapidly advancing engineering world, these skills are not sufficient for an individual to succeed in the profession [1][16][18]. As the role of engineering is evolving, individuals in the profession and those wishing to enter it require a knowledge of both the technical and transversal aspects of the discipline [1][5][16].

The transversal skills outlined as important requirements are extremely broad as noted in a number of studies [4][6][7][8][16]. Through investigations exploring desired engineering knowledge and skills, the magnitude of the transversal skills desired for engineers became apparent as they varied from communication, critical thinking, innovation, leadership and honesty, problem solving, reasoning and teamwork [1][4][5][7][8][16].

In past engineering education structures, there was little importance placed on these transversal abilities. Transversal skills were seen to be of little importance to the success of an individual in the profession as an in-depth technical knowledge was favoured for the types of problems that engineers faced during this time. Through the

evolution of the profession and education, transversal skills and their acquisition have become an area of greater importance [1][5][16][18].

2 SPATIAL ABILITY

Spatial ability is defined as the capacity of an individual to successfully mentally manipulate visual patterns [13]. It is also described as “the ability to generate, retain, retrieve, and transform well-structured visual images” [14]. Examples of these visual images include mental rotation, and the mental folding and unfolding of objects [20]. As earlier noted, spatial ability is an innate ability and therefore may not be directly developed. However, spatial skills may be developed to support an individual’s innate spatial ability when performing spatially orientated tasks. There are a range of measures available for the analysis of spatial skills such as the Mental Cutting Test (MCT) [21] and Purdue Spatial Visualisation Test and Rotations (PSVT: R) [22].

Fig. 1. Example of question on the MCT

Fig. 2. Example of question on the PSVT:R

It has been established that spatial ability and skills play an important role in success in STEM fields [12][15][19][23]. This perhaps is to be expected as spatial visualisation, an element of spatial ability, which involves the manipulation of 2D and 3D models, is a means of visually communicating [12]. This is a fundamental aspect of a number of STEM disciplines, particularly engineering.

2.1 Spatial Ability in Third-Level Engineering Education

Spatial abilities have been explored as neglected talents in education [10]. This is of great importance when one considers the role of these competencies in the engineering profession. Disciplines of engineering, such as mechanical engineering, are perceived as highly spatially orientated disciplines, while there is also recognition that all disciplines of engineering are spatially demanding [23]. The skills acquired and developed throughout engineering education programs are fundamental to the success of graduates in the profession [1][4].

The aim of education is to provide students with domain-specific knowledge [24], skills and abilities. The acquisition of such a broad range of competencies requires an individual to be proficient in the internalisation and externalisation of communications, and information processing [3]. However, spatial abilities are also important to this process for students of all engineering disciplines. Information is often communicated through visual means in engineering and engineering education e.g. through the use of parametric modelling software. Therefore, spatial abilities, such as retention or mental manipulation [13][14], are necessary to understand the information presented to support the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities.

The development of technical and transversal knowledge and skills through engineering education is fundamental to students succeeding in the profession upon completion of their studies [1][4]. Through the development of capacities which support the consolidation of information, such as spatial and communication skills, engineering education programmes will move towards achieving an integrated learning experience for engineering students.

3 ACHIEVING AN INTEGRATED ENGINEERING EDUCATION EXPERIENCE

An integrated education and learning experience requires the coming together of knowledge, skills, and abilities for the consolidation and understanding of information. Past engineering education programmes placed a greater emphasis on a deep technical knowledge, with lesser importance placed on skills and abilities, resulting in a fragmented approach to engineering education. Over time, a transition has occurred whereby engineering education frameworks have been moving towards an integrated educational experience, as illustrated in Figure 3 below.

Fig. 3. The evolution of attribute dominance in engineering education

Due to the nature of the engineering profession and the advancements in both technology and the complexity of engineering problems, the development of skills and abilities through engineering education has become an area of increasing importance [1][16][18]. As educational approaches have advanced, engineering skills have risen in importance and have begun to converge with engineering knowledge, illustrating the emphasis placed on these competencies in engineering education programmes.

While abilities have increased in importance, they still often do not receive the same emphasis as knowledge and skills. However, in order for an integrated experience to be achieved, greater emphasis must be placed on developing abilities as they are pivotal to the consolidation of knowledge and skills. For instance, if an individual cannot effectively communicate, problem solve or spatially reason, they may not be

able to consolidate the knowledge and skills that occur throughout their education and learning experience.

3.1 Spatial Ability and Integrated Education

Although an integrated educational experience may be provided for students, this does not mean that integrated learning takes place. In order for this experience to be translated into learning, the underlying skills that support the processing and understanding of information must be developed. Though communication skills and information processing are central to understanding information [3], consideration must be made for the fact that engineering is a highly spatially orientated profession [23].

Spatial ability is central to the acquisition and development of both technical and transversal knowledge and skills [4][5][7][8][9][10][11][12], while also playing an important role in problem solving [25]. Knowledge and skill acquisition, and problem solving are core elements of engineering and engineering education programmes. Due to the role of spatial ability in fundamental factors of engineering education, the development of such a competency may support an integrated education and learning experience being achieved.

The development of biologically secondary abilities such as domain-specific knowledge and skills [24] is the fundamental focus of education. As earlier noted, spatial ability cannot be directly developed as it is an innate biologically primary ability. However, spatial skills, as biologically secondary abilities, can be developed through education and training to support an individual's innate spatial ability. This is a core element that must be considered in the context of engineering education, due to the role of spatial ability and skill in engineering practice.

Spatial skills may be developed in a number of ways throughout engineering education due to the spatially orientated nature of the discipline. Problem solving is a central element of engineering education programmes such as Problem-Based Learning and Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate [26]. The problem solving experience provides an organic opportunity for spatial skills to be developed in a practical context through engineering education.

Students may be encouraged to sketch, produce a physical model, or a parametric model [9] to support them in reaching a solution. Engagement in such an experience provides the student with the opportunity to generate, retain, and retrieve visual imagery. In this context, the completion of the sketch or model supports the development of the student's spatial skills, complementing the underlying spatial ability to reach a solution. Completing a task of this nature also requires the student to call on their knowledge, skills, and abilities to reason about the solution. Leading to an integrated learning experience being achieved whereby knowledge, skills, and abilities are consolidated through the completion of a spatially orientated task.

As problem solving is utilised in a number of engineering education programmes to bring together knowledge, skills, and abilities, achieving an integrated education and learning experience would require minimal structural change to existing curricula. Rather, the focus would be placed on capitalising on the natural relationship that exists between engineering and spatial abilities and skills. Through placing a greater emphasis on elements such as sketching and modelling throughout the problem solving process, educators may ensure the knowledge, skills, and abilities are consolidated and that students have a complete understanding of the complex

relationships that exist between objects and space in engineering e.g. forces, machine processes.

As the engineering profession and engineering education evolve, it is pivotal that core skills such as spatial skills are developed to support students succeeding in the profession and adapting to future changes. Therefore, it is vital that an integrated learning experience is achieved through the delivery of an integrated educational approach so that engineering graduates may successfully perform in their future roles.

4 SUMMARY

Spatial skills play a fundamental role in the engineering profession and in the acquisition and development of technical and transversal knowledge and skills. In order for engineering graduates to be successful in the profession, an emphasis must be placed on the development of fundamental abilities and to support the consolidation of learning experiences. Spatial skills are extremely important in engineering education and to success in STEM disciplines as they support students capacity to be creative, innovative and problem solve, each of which are highlighted as key desirable attributes of engineers by prospective employers and professional engineering bodies [1][6][7]. While there has been considerable progression in the approach taken to third-level engineering education, this progress must continue to ensure that graduate engineers are provided with the opportunity to be successful in the engineering profession.

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